

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF EARLY DIAGNOSING AND TREATMENT OF DEGENERATIVE AND DYSTROPHIC DISEASES OF THE HEM.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7651862>

Relevance of the problem. Degenerative changes in the pelvis and hips occur at almost the same rate in the population of developed countries. Thus, among the poorest sections of the population of Southeast Asia, the frequency of specific degenerative changes in the pelvic area is only 30%, but among the population of those regions growing up in prosperity, almost the same pain 100% of adults experienced this disease.

Disruption of pelvic biomechanics affects the localization of degenerative changes and trauma. Disruption of physiological biomechanics depending on the characteristics of nutrition and forced lifestyle changes are the precursors of the development of dystrophic-degenerative changes in the pelvis. Inflammation of the femoral head, which is usually present, is also a risk factor for the development of degenerative processes of the pelvis. The hyaline in the joint space leads to displacement and the formation of reactive bone changes in this zone -

The level of studying the problem. Degenerative-dystrophic changes in the hip joint are primarily dangerous because they can turn into a chronic pathology. Approximately 85% of patients with degenerative-dystrophic pathologies complain of constant pain in the leg and pelvis area.

There are many degenerative causes of the hip joint, the main factors are; metabolic processes and blood circulation disorders in a certain part of the pelvic area; lack of nutrients in bone and bone tissue; injury to the head of the femur, as well as syndromes after KOV-19; excessive burden on himself; Improper and frequent weight lifting; stretching ligaments, muscles; joint space microspasm; infectious processes at the beginning of the thigh; hormonal disorders; inflammatory processes in the body; harmful habits; poor nutrition; overweight; sedentary lifestyle, sedentary work; Age-related changes in tissues, improper nutrition of tissues; genetic reasons. The list of reasons clearly indicates various factors that can lead to the development of degenerative-dystrophic diseases of the pelvic-hip area.

Research objectives:

- conducting a clinical and anamnestic analysis to determine the early manifestations of degenerative diseases of the hip joint;
- to study the early clinical manifestations, causes and risk factors of degenerative diseases of the femoral head;
- identification of early pathomorphological signs of degenerative changes in the soft tissues of the femoral head;
- to identify the initial pathomorphological signs of degenerative changes in the bone tissues of the pelvis;
- development of an algorithm of initial diagnostic signs of degenerative changes in the femoral head.

Scientific and practical significance of the study Information on the characteristics of early clinical, anamnestic and instrumental data on degenerative-dystrophic diseases of the hip joint allows for the development of necessary therapeutic measures.

Determining the specifics of early clinical manifestations, causes and risk factors of the development of degenerative diseases of the pelvis allows to understand the characteristic initial symptoms of these diseases.

